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Executive Summary

Renewable methanol (MeOH) is considered an important fuel for hard-to-abate transport sectors and a key platform chemical for the defossilisation of products and services. The ēQATOR concept enables the production of renewable MeOH from biogas ($\text{CH}_4 + \text{CO}_2$) derived from biomass residues and biogenic waste. The biogas will first be transformed via a reforming reaction into syngas ($\text{CO} + \text{H}_2$) in electrically-heated catalytic reactors, followed by the actual MeOH synthesis in a second step. The reforming reaction requires high heat input at elevated temperatures, conventionally supplied by methane combustion (usually in the form of natural gas, but biomethane would also be possible).

A comprehensive integrated life cycle sustainability assessment will be completed to support informed decision-making for both technology development and policy frameworks. The assessment will be based on three separate analyses of the classical pillars of sustainability, environmental, social and economic. The present study specifically addresses the environmental performance of the ēQATOR concept. A screening-type prospective Life Cycle Assessment has evaluated the extent to which the ēQATOR concept can contribute to a more sustainable MeOH supply. The assessment follows ISO 14040 and 14044 and applies a cradle-to-grave perspective. Key environmental impact categories are analysed for 2030 and 2050 using projected European electricity mixes, consumables and infrastructure. Environmental hotspots, optimisation potentials and differences between ēQATOR configurations have been identified. The production of ēQATOR MeOH is compared with that for fossil-fuel derived MeOH and renewable MeOH by alternative pathways, including biogas upgrading, other hybrid reforming options and fully synthetic MeOH from direct air capture of CO_2 and water electrolysis. Further analyses consider the availability of renewable resources in relation to future MeOH demand, as well as the classification and greenhouse gas (GHG) performance of ēQATOR MeOH under the EU legislative framework (Renewable Energy Directive).

The results show that all renewable MeOH pathways — including hybrid concepts such as ēQATOR — offer significant environmental benefits compared with fossil-fuel derived MeOH production, particularly when low-carbon electricity is used. Hybrid pathways combining biogenic carbon from waste- and residue-derived biogas with renewable electricity utilise the available carbon more efficiently than purely bio-based routes. Compared with fully synthetic MeOH, hybrid pathways require less renewable electricity. Given the limited availability of sustainable carbon sources and renewable electricity, these hybrid routes therefore represent the most efficient long-term option. Nevertheless, all renewable pathways will be needed to meet future demand, supplemented by measures to reduce overall MeOH consumption.

For both hybrid and synthetic pathways, the carbon intensity of the electricity supply dominates the environmental performance, whereas process choices (e.g., heating technology and reforming configuration), infrastructure and materials play only a secondary role. The choice of biomass feedstock is also of secondary importance, when considering that it is currently already in use. Additional environmental benefits can be achieved by using previously untapped manure. Especially when using fully renewable electricity, additional optimisation lies in reducing methane emissions from biogas systems, mitigating hydrogen emissions and carefully managing environmental side effects associated with renewable energy deployment. While ēQATOR MeOH can be classified as co-production of advanced biofuels and renewable fuels of non-biological origin, achievement of the required GHG emission savings strongly depends on the type of biomass residue or biogenic waste used and on the emission intensity of the electricity supply.

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1 Introduction

Worldwide, more than 110 million tonnes (t) of methanol (MeOH) are produced annually [1], mainly from fossil resources such as natural gas or coal, and demand is growing. In addition to reducing the environmental impact of fossil-fuel based MeOH, it is essential to produce MeOH from sustainable renewable resources so as to minimise the environmental impact of MeOH used as an energy carrier or as a platform chemical for many different end products such as resins, foams, binders and plastics.

Biogas from biomass residues or biogenic wastes, for instance from manure, the organic fraction of municipal solid waste (OF-MSW) or wastewater, is a sustainable renewable resource. One synthetic process for producing MeOH from biogas involves producing syngas, a mixture of carbon monoxide (CO) and hydrogen (H₂). However, this production method requires a significant amount of energy in the catalytic reforming reactor. To maximise carbon yield, this energy should ideally be provided by renewable electricity, thereby avoiding the use of biogas for process heat and ensuring that all the carbon content in the biogas is retained in the MeOH product rather than a portion released as carbon dioxide (CO₂). To this end, the aims to develop scalable, electrically heated catalytic reactor technologies that will allow the conversion of biogas, a mixture of methane (CH₄) and CO₂, into syngas with improved efficiency compared to the state-of-the-art technology.

1.1 The ēQATOR concept

Two different technologies for heating the reforming reactor electrically instead of fuelling it conventionally with natural gas will be tested, resistive and microwave heating (RH and MWH, respectively). By heating only the catalyst support, gains in efficiency and sustainability over conventional heating with fossil fuels will be realised. Two different processes for the transformation of both the CO₂ and CH₄ in the biogas to syngas will be tested, Dry Reforming (DR) and Mixed Reforming (MR). DR uses only CO₂ and CH₄ as feed, but the process has a CO₂ recycle step to increase the CO₂:CH₄ ratio in the feed gas to reduce catalyst coking and deactivation. MR addresses the coking challenge by adding water (H₂O) to the feed. The project bridges biogas production with downstream conversion technologies into higher value-added products, in this case into MeOH, a platform chemical.

Figure 1 shows the process flow diagram (PFD) for the ēQATOR system producing renewable MeOH from biogas. Residues or wastes of biological origin are converted to biogas, a mixture of mainly CH₄ and CO₂ plus a number of other gaseous compounds, in conventional anaerobic digestion plants. Digestate is obtained as a co-product. In addition to the anaerobic digestion plants' standard purification, further purification (upgrading) is necessary to meet the requirements of the downstream catalysts. Subsequently, the biogas is converted into syngas in the electrically-heated reforming reactor. This step is the focus of the ēQATOR research and development. Additional renewable H₂ is added to achieve the desired stoichiometric ratio for the subsequent MeOH synthesis. This last step uses state-of-the-art technology.

Figure 1. Simplified PFD of the ēQATOR concept involving MeOH production from biogas obtained from anaerobic digestion of biomass residues or wastes via syngas.

1.2 Sustainability assessment within ēQATOR

In the project, an integrated life cycle sustainability assessment (ILCSA) will be performed to analyse all three pillars of sustainability, environment, society and economy. The main objective of the ILCSA is a comparison of selected scenarios for the conversion of biogas into MeOH, including the identification of optimisation potentials as well as conclusions and recommendations to support a sustainable deployment of the value chain and the adoption of the developed products by industry.

As one of the three separate analyses that are ultimately integrated the ILCSA, the present study focuses on the environmental performance of the ēQATOR concept. Three elements for analysis were foreseen, of which one element was optional.

- An environmental **life cycle assessment (LCA)** is based on the principles of comprehensiveness and life cycle thinking (LCT) to achieve reliable and robust recommendations for future investments in sustainable technology. LCT means that all life cycle stages for products are considered, i.e., the complete supply or value chains, from biomass and energy production, through chemical conversion and production of the end user products, to product use and end-of-life treatment or final disposal. Through such a systematic overview, the unintentional shifting of environmental burdens between life cycle stages or individual processes can be identified and minimised or preferably avoided. The sustainability performance of each product and co-product is compared to alternative reference products. Due to its comprehensive approach, it should be the main basis of decision-making policy and will be the main focus of the analysis.
- A classification and calculation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emission savings according to the European **Renewable Energy Directive (RED, Directive (EU) 2018/2001 [2])** on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources and its amendments and revisions) will ensure compliance with current legislation towards a more sustainable future. This legally unambiguous calculation is an important decision-making aid for investment decisions.
- In cases where relevant local environmental impacts occur that cannot be adequately captured using the LCA methodology, an optional **life cycle environmental impact assessment (LC-EIA)** was envisaged. LC-EIA generalises elements of a classical EIA [3], which qualitatively assesses environmental factors at site and project level, and applies them to all life cycle stages. The environmental factors covered include human beings, fauna and flora, soil, water, air, climate, landscape, material assets and the cultural heritage. Significant local environmental impacts are generally expected when dedicated biomass crops are used as a consequence of the associated land occupation for cultivation. The ēQATOR concept, however, relies on biomass residues and biogenic waste, which in contrast to dedicated biomass crops, are not linked to land occupation. In many cases, biomass residues and biogenic waste are already used today, e.g., for biogas production (manure), or collected and otherwise utilised (e.g., for composting of OF-MSW). Due to the nature of the feedstocks and the absence of relevant *additional* local environmental impacts, it was decided not to conduct an LC-EIA within the scope of ēQATOR.

Therefore, the environmental aspects of the ēQATOR concept are assessed based on LCA and a GHG balance in accordance with the RED. The results of these analyses, together with the social and techno-economic assessments, will be summarised by the ILCSA in a comprehensive sustainability assessment as part of the Public Deliverable D.6.6 *Integrated sustainability assessment report*.

2 Definitions and settings

Both the LCA and the GHG balance according to the RED build on definitions and settings that are

common to all assessments contributing to the ILCSA. These definitions and settings are set out in Section 2.1. Specific definitions and settings that are only relevant to the environmental assessment are defined separately in Sections 2.2 and 2.3.

2.1 Common definitions and settings for the ILCSA

2.1.1 Goal definition

The comprehensiveness and level of detail of the sustainability assessment can vary considerably depending on its goal. Therefore, the intended applications, the reasons for carrying out the study, the decision context, the target audiences and – if applicable – the commissioning body of the LCA study must be described.

Aim of the study and target audience

The main aim of the study is to provide decision support in two main areas.

- Identification of the sustainability implications of ēQATOR pathways.
- Identification of all optimisation potentials for both processes and complete scenarios.

The target audience of the study is decision makers in the fields of politics, research and industry and the general public.

Guiding questions

Against this background, the main guiding question to be answered by the ILCSA and thus the environmental assessments is defined as follows.

- To what extent and under which conditions can the ēQATOR concept contribute to a more sustainable supply of MeOH?

This question is restricted to the following comparison:

- **How does the ēQATOR MeOH perform against natural gas-derived MeOH produced via Steam Methane Reforming (SMR) in a conventionally fired reactor?**

Addressing the main question, consequently, leads to the following sub-questions:

- Which unit processes and (co-)product uses significantly determine the results and what are the optimisation potentials?
- Is there a difference, and if so, is the difference significant, between
 - Biogas from manure and biogas from OF-MSW?
 - DR and MR?
 - RH and MWH?
- Are the ēQATOR project's Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to economy, environment and society met?
 - Zero direct local emissions from heating
 - Reduction in CO₂ footprint of at least 60 % on the projected 2030 EU energy mix, up to 91 % for certain renewable energy sources (off-shore wind)
 - 60-80 % reduction of GHG emissions compared to a SMR reference scenario, including power sources (cables, housing, etc.) for a 1 MW unit

The consortium decided that the partners responsible for each assessment can decide whether to include further questions and sub-questions in their analysis. Further questions answered by the LCA and the GHG balance according to the RED are therefore specified in Sections 2.2 and 2.3.

2.1.2 Scope definition

The scope of an ILCSA study involves defining the subject of the study, including the exact products and relevant systems to be analysed. The scope should be sufficiently well defined to ensure that the comprehensiveness, depth and level of detail of the study are consistent with and sufficient to achieve the stated goal (see Section 2.1.1). The following common scope definition applies to all analyses within the ILCSA. The specific scope definition for the LCA study is set out in Section 2.2.2.

System boundary

System boundaries specify which unit processes belong to the production system and are thus included in the assessment. In order to avoid shifting burdens to other life cycle stages, the entire life cycle (value chain) must be analysed from cradle to grave, i.e., from the production of inputs to the end-of-life of the products, see Figure 2. In the case of ēQATOR, the entire life cycle of MeOH production from biogas includes the feedstock provision, the production of biogas via anaerobic digestion, the purification of the biogas, the reforming step, MeOH synthesis, the use of MeOH and the end-of-life. This study does not include a detailed modelling of the ‘utilisation’ stage, as MeOH is used as a platform chemical for a wide variety of applications, either as a building block for chemical derivatives or as a fuel. In addition, the MeOH produced via the ēQATOR process and via the reference system is chemically identical. For these two reasons, the analysis of the ‘utilisation’ stage is omitted for the comparison of the systems. However, this simplification must be taken into account when interpreting the results.

Figure 2. System boundary (cradle-to-grave) of the ēQATOR system. The different frame types represent the level of detail in which the life cycle stages are analysed: dashed, not considered; bold, very detailed.

As the ēQATOR project is developing electrically-heated reforming reactors, the project partners have developed detailed models primarily for the ‘purification & reforming’ step. As a result, the level of detail varies for the different life cycle stages. The frame types used in Figure 2 represent this level of detail.

Functional unit

MeOH is a platform chemical serving as a substrate for the production of various higher value-added products. It is often traded according to International Methanol Producers and Consumers Association specifications [4]. This is a standard for technical aspects of the MeOH involving limits for the purity. The functional unit to answer the main question and the compulsory sub-questions is thus ‘1 tonne of MeOH with a purity of 99.85 %’.

Technical reference

Mature technology at industrial scale (‘nth plant’) is analysed. The technologies developed by the various partners are at lab scale for the MWH system (Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 5) or at pilot scale for the RH system (TRL 6). The data generated is thus extrapolated by process simulation and supplemented with expert opinion and literature data to model the realistic industrial scale equivalents of such technologies to allow for a fair comparison with the already existing mature technologies.

The capacity of the commercial-scale biogas plant was defined by the consortium, see Table 1. For

both biogas feedstocks (manure and OF-MSW), a raw biogas flow of 500 Nm³/h is set. This requires a biomass input of approximately 160 000 m³/yr of liquid manure and 45 000 t/yr of OF-MSW [5], corresponding to 8 000 – 9 000 livestock units [6] and 400 000 – 800 000 inhabitants, respectively [7].

Table 1. Anaerobic digester size, feedstock quantities and providers for a commercial-scale biogas plant.

	Biogas from manure	Biogas from OF-MSW
Dry biogas (raw)	500 Nm ³ /h	500 Nm ³ /h
Feedstock	160 000 m ³ /yr manure	45 000 t/yr OF-MSW
Providers	≈ 8 000 – 9 000 livestock units	≈ 400 000 – 800 000 inhabitants

Time frame

The definition of a time frame is important for specific background data, e.g. for power generation. Although a mature, full-scale industrial plant is not expected to be operating before 2035, the consortium agreed to set 2030 as the reference year for the ILCSA in ēQATOR due to better data availability for years divisible by 10.

Geographical coverage

The ILCSA in ēQATOR geographically covers Europe (EU + EEA + UK + CH). This means that process data with corresponding geographical coverage is selected if available.

2.1.3 Settings for Life Cycle Inventory

Data sources

Primary data on mass and energy balances for the ‘purification & reforming’ step were obtained from process simulations using Aspen Plus[®] software. The simulations are based on literature data and original research data from the ēQATOR project partners. The data required for the mass and energy balance for the ‘anaerobic digestion’ step was provided by the European Biogas Association and literature references. The mass and energy balance for the ‘MeOH synthesis’ step is provided by SINTEF and Equinor ASA. The data for the reference systems are derived from literature references by the authors of this study.

Infrastructure

Infrastructure is considered to distinguish between scenarios (especially heating systems). Information on infrastructure for the ēQATOR pathways were provided from models of the equipment as derived from the process simulation.

2.2 Specific definitions and settings for LCA

LCA is based on International Organisation for Standardization (ISO) standards [8, 9] and the International Reference Life Cycle Data System (ILCD) guidelines [10]. The screening LCA study carried out largely follows these standards and guidelines. Specific settings, methodological choices and deviations from these standards and guidelines are described in detail below. Moreover, settings specific to the LCA which are not covered by the common definitions and settings for the ILCSA (see Section 2.1) are detailed.

2.2.1 Introduction to LCA methodology

LCA is structured, comprehensive and internationally standardised by ISO standards 14040:2006 and 14044:2006 [8, 9]. According to the ISO standards, an LCA consists of four iterative phases (compare Figure 3):

- Goal and scope definition (see Sections 2.1.1 and 2.2.2)
- Inventory analysis (see Sections 2.1.3 and 2.2.3),

- Impact assessment (see Sections 2.2.4 and 4.1 to 4.3), and
- Interpretation (see Section 5).

Figure 3. Phases of an LCA [8, 9].

ISO standards 14040 and 14044 provide the indispensable framework for LCA. This framework, however, leaves the individual LCA analyst with a range of choices that can affect the legitimacy of the results of an LCA study. While flexibility is essential to respond to the wide variety of questions addressed, further guidance is needed to support consistency and quality assurance.

The ILCD Handbook [10] has, therefore, been developed to provide guidance and specifications that go beyond the ISO 14040 and 14044 standards, aiming at consistent and quality-assured LCA data and studies. The screening LCA study carried out within the ēQATOR project takes into account the main requirements of the ILCD Handbook following the considerations of flexibility and strictness. The analyses in this study are the so-called screening LCAs which follow the above-mentioned ISO standards except for the level of detail of the documentation, the number of sensitivity analyses and the mandatory critical review. Nevertheless, the results of these screening LCAs are suitable for reliably answering the guiding questions due to their close conformity with the ISO standards.

2.2.2 Supplements to goal and scope definition

The LCA covers all goals and scopes as defined for the ILCSA in Sections 2.1.1 and 2.1.2. Additionally, the LCA aims to answer following guiding question:

- How does the ēQATOR MeOH perform against MeOH derived from sustainable biogenic and atmospheric carbon sources?

Functional unit

In addition to the functional unit '1 tonne of MeOH with a purity of 99.85 %', the functional unit '1 MJ of MeOH' is used for a further analysis. Hereby, the mass of MeOH is converted into energy with the lower heating value (LHV) of 19.95 MJ/kg on a dry basis [11].

2.2.3 Settings for the Life Cycle Inventory

Time frame

In addition to the reference year 2030, the reference year 2050 will be analysed to compare the ēQATOR scenarios with MeOH derived from sustainable biogenic and atmospheric carbon sources, to evaluate the ēQATOR concept against other defossilisation-compatible pathways.

Data sources

Data for the foreground process were based on the mass and energy balances used for ILCSA. Data on biogas provision were based on an ifeu-internal database. Data on background processes were taken from the ifeu-internal prospective life cycle inventory (LCI) database 'LCAsT' [12], which is based on ecoinvent v3.7.1 [13]. The database was developed within the REFINE project [14], funded

by the German Federal Environment Agency (Umweltbundesamt). It models three normative transformation scenarios for achieving climate neutrality in Germany by 2050, as defined in the RESCUE project [15], and combines these with transformation pathways by Teske et al. [16] for developments in Europe and the rest of the world. For the present analysis, the 'GreenLate' scenario [17] was selected, as it aligned most closely with the remaining options for achieving climate neutrality by 2050. LCAst contains LCI data for products including electricity, consumables and infrastructure covering the period up to 2050 in 10-year increments. The mass and energy balances of reference scenarios were based on literature data (for details see Section 3.2).

Infrastructure

Proprietary data for catalyst manufacturing were provided by Johnson Matthey plc. Information on material inputs including infrastructure for the ēQATOR pathways were provided by SINTEF (see Section 2.1.3). Since detailed information on durability and end-of-life scenarios of all used materials were not available from within the project, approximations based on generic data sets fill gaps. Data on infrastructure for reference scenarios were taken from literature.

Attributional vs. consequential modelling

Sustainability assessment can follow either a consequential or an attributional approach. This choice has implications for the methodological approach regarding co-products and indirect effects. Consequential modelling is more extensive and 'aims at identifying the consequences that a decision in the foreground system has for other processes and systems of the economy' according to the ILCD Handbook [18]. This is recommended for decision contexts where influential impacts are expected to occur at the meso/macro level [18], such as for the ēQATOR systems. Therefore, a consequential modelling approach has been applied in this assessment.

Co-products handling

As outlined in Section 2.1.2, the system boundary includes all products (i.e. MeOH) and co-products (digestate and heat, depending on the process). Figure 4 illustrates the general alternatives concerning the procedure of co-product handling in the example of rapeseed oil, system expansion (substitution) and allocation. According to ISO standards for LCA [8, 9], system expansion is preferable to allocation. In the context of system expansion, credits are given for avoiding environmental burdens associated with the substituted reference products. This reduces the (main)

Figure 4. Illustration of methodological approaches for co-product handling.

product's environmental impact.

Biogenic carbon

Atmospheric CO₂ plays an integral role in the Earth's carbon cycle. CO₂ can be removed from the atmosphere by both natural processes (photosynthesis) and technical processes (e.g. direct air capture, DAC). When removed via biomass growth, it is referred to as biogenic carbon. If a product that contains carbon removed from the atmosphere (by either process) is combusted (in an engine) or incinerated (in a waste incineration plant) at the end of its lifetime, the amount of CO₂ released into the atmosphere equals the amount of CO₂ that had been taken up recently (short carbon cycle). Given that the lifetime of most MeOH-based end products is less than 100 years, carbon storage in the product is not considered. A timely sequence of CO₂ uptake and release (often within one year) thus does not affect atmospheric CO₂ concentrations. For many years, LCA practitioners considered this to be neutral until the ILCD Handbook made it mandatory to include CO₂ uptake and release in the LCA model. In this study, however, these fluxes are not displayed in the result graphs for reasons of simplicity and clarity. The release of fossil CO₂ (taken up a long time ago; long carbon cycle), in contrast, increases atmospheric CO₂ concentrations and contributes to global warming. This is, of course, accounted for and displayed explicitly in the result graphs.

2.2.4 Settings for Life Cycle Impact Assessment

According to ISO standard 14040 [8], Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) includes the mandatory steps of classification and characterisation and the optional steps of normalisation and weighting. Classification and characterisation depend on the selected impact categories and LCIA methods. Regarding the optional elements, only the normalisation step is applied within the ēQATOR project. The corresponding specifications of these LCIA elements are described in the following sections.

Impact categories and LCIA methods

All main environmental issues related to the ēQATOR value chains should be comprehensively covered within the impact categories of the screening LCA. Furthermore, the impact categories must be consistent with the goal of the study and the intended applications of the results. Potential environmental impacts can be analysed at the midpoint or endpoint levels. For environmental assessments within technology development projects such as ēQATOR, the midpoint level is considered to be more appropriate than the endpoint level because the impacts are analysed in a more differentiated way and the results are more accurate. The chosen LCIA methods essentially follow the recommendations of Detzel et al. [19]. Despite being slightly outdated, these methods were chosen due to their compatibility with the prospective electricity data sets available from the REFINE project.

The impact categories 'eutrophication, freshwater', 'photochemical ozone formation' and 'phosphate rock use' are excluded from further analysis in all cases since data quality is insufficient to assess differences between systems or scenarios. The impact category 'ionising radiation' is considered irrelevant for the ēQATOR value chains and thus completely excluded from this study. Furthermore, the impact category 'toxicity' is excluded due to insufficient data quality for the reference year 2030. However, specific human health issues are covered by the category particulate matter formation.

Although the impact category 'water use' could be relevant for the ēQATOR scenario and its reference scenarios, it was excluded from the analysis due to limited data availability. In the foreground system, key boundary conditions remain undefined due to the lower TRL of the ēQATOR technology and the project's focus on reactor and catalyst development. For instance, cooling technologies, digester types and the plant's final location are not yet known. For the background system, water flows associated with the electricity mixes lack validity and spatial resolution. This

limitation should be addressed and optimised once the ēQATOR technology reaches a higher TRL.

H₂ plays an important role in ēQATOR and causes indirect warming by influencing atmospheric CH₄, tropospheric ozone and stratospheric water vapor, with CH₄ dominating. The absolute value of its GWP remains under scientific discussion and depends on the CH₄ concentration. For the purpose of this study, the GWP₁₀₀ of 10 according to Chen et al. [20] is used. Table 2 lists all midpoint indicators investigated and the underlying LCIA method. The abbreviations in the Table are later used in Figures for clarity.

Table 2. Overview of investigated midpoint impact categories.

Midpoint impact category	Indicator (abbreviation)	LCIA method
Climate change	Global warming potential (GWP)	[21] IPCC 2021, no LT, incl. SLCFs and H ₂ ^a
Acidification	Acidification potential (AP)	[22]
Eutrophication, terrestrial	Terrestrial eutrophication potential (TEP)	[22]
Particulate matter formation	Particulate matter formation (PMF)	[23]
Ozone depletion	Ozone depletion potential (ODP)	[24, 25]
Non-renewable energy use	Non-renewable energy use (NREU)	[26, 27]
Land use	Distance-to-nature potential (LU)	[28]

^a IPCC = Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. LT = long-term. SLCF = short-lived climate forcers.

Normalisation

Normalisation is an optional step in LCA to better understand the relative magnitude of the results for the different environmental impact categories. It does this by relating the category indicator results to reference information. Normalisation transforms an indicator result by dividing it by a selected reference value, e.g., a certain emission caused by the system is divided by the corresponding emission per capita in a selected country or region.

In ēQATOR, the value chains are characterised for Europe. Therefore, resource demand and emissions per capita in the Europe are chosen as references for normalisation. The latest available data from Sala et al. [29] and Fehrenbach et al. [28] are used. These values refer to the year 2010 and the EU-28 countries. The resulting inhabitant equivalents (IEs) can be converted to non-normalised values by the resource demand and emissions per capita listed in Table 3. While the reference values per capita are from 2010, the LCA results refer to the years 2030 and 2050. This must be taken into account when interpreting the LCA results on an IE basis.

Table 3. Resource demand and emissions per capita in the EU 28 in 2010 for relevant environmental indicators.

Environmental indicator	Resource demand and emissions per capita	
Climate change (GWP) ^a	9.2	t CO ₂ equivalent/(inhabitant · year)
Acidification (AP) ^a	35	kg SO ₂ equivalent/(inhabitant · year)
Terrestrial eutrophication (TEP) ^a	5.5	kg PO ₄ equivalent/(inhabitant · year)
Particulate matter (PMF) ^a	28	kg PM2.5 equivalent/(inhabitant · year)
Ozone depletion (ODP) ^a	0.056	kg CFC-11 equivalent/inhabitant · year)
Non-renewable energy use (NREU) ^a	34	MJ/(inhabitant · year)
Land use (LU) ^b	0.24	ha artificial land equivalent/inhabitant

^a Ref. [29]. ^b Ref. [28].

Weighting

Weighting uses numerical factors based on value choices to compare and sometimes aggregate indicator results that are not physically comparable. Weighting is not applied in this study.

2.3 Specific settings for a GHG balance according to RED

2.3.1 Introduction to RED

The European Union promotes the expansion of renewable energy with the help of the Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2023/2413 (RED III, [30]), a revision of Directive (EU) 2018/2011 (RED II, [2]), which in turn builds on the earlier Directive (EU) 2009/28/EC [31]. The delegated acts (DAs) 2023/1184 and 2023/1185 [32, 33] supplement RED II and RED III. The commission implementing regulation 2022/996 [11] lays down calculation rules and default values for the GHG intensities of inputs. Since then, several revisions of the directive, the DA and the implementing regulation have entered into force. For the sake of clarity, the legal framework as of January 2026 is referred to as 'RED' below.

The primary objective of the RED is to increase the share of renewable energy in the EU's final energy consumption to at least 42.5 % by 2030, with an ambitious target of 45 %. It aims to decarbonise all sectors, in particular transport, industry and heating, by setting binding targets and sustainability criteria for renewable energy sources. To this end, the RED sets the share of renewable energy and the use of certain fuels such as advanced biofuels, renewable fuels of non-biological origin (RFNBOs) and recycled carbon fuels. The targets must be transposed into national law by May 2025.

2.3.2 Regulations applying specifically to ēQATOR

The ēQATOR project aims to produce a combination of **advanced biofuels** and **RFNBOs** from biogas made from manure or OF-MSW (see feedstocks listed in RED III, Annex IX, Part A [30]) by electric heating and adding H₂ from the electrolysis of water. The share of advanced biofuels and RFNBOs can be determined by analysing the relevant shares of energy content derived from either the biomass feedstock or the renewable electricity contributing to the heating value of the product (DA 2023/1185, Annex A.3 [33]). The MeOH produced with the ēQATOR concept may thus not only contribute to the overall RED objective but can also contribute to the several other sectoral targets.

In the **transport sector**, at least 5.5 % of the energy consumed must come from advanced biofuels or RFNBOs. Advanced biofuels can count towards this target with double their energy content. To be counted as advanced biofuels, the associated GHG emissions must be at least 65 % below those of a fossil fuel comparator (RED III, Article 29, Section 10. C [30]) if they are produced in facilities that entered into operation in 2021 or later. The respective fossil fuel comparator is 94 g CO₂-eq/MJ fuel (RED III, Annex V, C 19 [30]). A reduction of 70 % is necessary for RFNBOs.

In the **industrial sector**, at least 42 % of the total H₂ used for final energy and non-energy purposes must comply with the delegated acts on RFNBOs in 2030 (DA 2023/1184 and DA 2023/1185 [32, 33]), with this share increasing to 60 % by 2035. H₂ used for synthesis could be considered as a RFNBO if GHG emissions savings are at least 70 % compared to the same fossil fuel comparator above and renewable electricity is used. Then, MeOH cannot be counted as a RFNBO for another sector.

If the MeOH is used as a biofuel **for electricity, heating and cooling** production, GHG savings must be at least 70 %, and in some cases even 80 %, compared to a fossil fuel comparator, depending on the date when the installation started operation (RED III, Article 29, Section 10. d-h [30]). The fossil fuel comparator is 183 g CO₂-eq/MJ for electricity and 80 g CO₂-eq/MJ for heating or cooling (RED III, Annex V, C 19 [30]). Moreover, the installation providing electricity, heating or cooling must be either small (< 50 MW thermal input), highly efficient or combined with biomass CO₂ capture and storage (RED III, Article 29, Section 11 [30]).

2.3.3 GHG balance

Calculation rules

The rules for calculating the GHG impact are set out in two annexes to RED, Annex V for biofuels and bioliquids and Annex VI for biomass fuels and further specified in Commission implementing regulation 2022/996. Calculation rules for RFNBOs are laid out in DA 2023/1185 [33].

The calculation rules under the RED follow a significantly different approach than the ISO standards 14040 and 14044 (see Section 2.2.1), as the RED calculation rules were created to verify compliance with the GHG saving criteria for each individual shipment of fuel. For this purpose, as stated in recital 116 of the RED, the so-called energy allocation method was considered to be the most appropriate method for the accounting for co-products. However, the so-called substitution method (which is more in line with the ISO standard) should be used for policy analysis.

Data sources

The data for the GHG intensities of inputs and energy were taken from Commission implementing regulation 2022/996 [11] to the extent possible. For all inputs not included in the respective lists, data from the LCA were used (see Section 2.2.3).

3 Analysed systems

3.1 The ēQATOR concepts

The production of MeOH in ēQATOR, via syngas generated from biogas, renewable electricity and renewable H₂, is shown in Figure 5 as a simple PFD, illustrating the main inputs, outputs and processes. More detailed PFDs can be found in Figures A1 to A3 in the Appendix. The ēQATOR process, shown with a bold frame, will be discussed in further detail below.

Figure 5. Simplified PFD of the ēQATOR process providing MeOH from biogas, renewable electricity and renewable H₂. More detailed PFDs can be found in Figures A1 to A3 in the Appendix.

Two different scenarios are considered to assess the impact of biogas dependent on the previous feedstock use.

- A) Biogas is already produced and used for the production of electricity in an on-site combined heat and power (CHP) plant. Part of the heat produced is used for fermenter heating. Installing ēQATOR leads to forgone credits for electricity production but also to avoided emissions (environmental burdens) from burning the biogas. The forgone credits and emissions depend on the CH₄ content of the biogas, slightly differing for manure and OF-MSW, but do not

consider emissions and resource uses along the value chain of the biogas production.

- B) The substrate for the biogas is not used for energy purposes until ēQATOR is installed, so a new biogas plant, a conventional anaerobic digester, needs to be built for this purpose. Taking sustainability aspects and long-term availability into account, two different biogenic feedstocks for the biogas production were selected, manure as an agricultural residue and OF-MSW. The impact of the feedstocks was assessed according to their current use in the absence of biogas production. This so-called counterfactual scenario involves the spreading of manure on fields and the composting of OF-MSW, replacing fossil-based fertilisers in agriculture and organic substrates in horticulture, respectively. The same approach is taken when assessing the co-produced digestate, thus considering differences in fertiliser value.

Biogas contains a number of other gaseous compounds in addition to CH_4 and CO_2 . The digester is equipped with a standard desulphurisation unit which adds a small amount of oxygen (O_2) to lower the sulphur content of the raw biogas. The representative composition of the biogas considered in this project is shown in Table A1 in the Appendix.

The raw biogas is further purified to meet the requirements of the downstream catalysts. The purification includes an additional desulphurisation module and a wet scrubbing section to remove ammonia (NH_3). The desulphurisation module can also remove siloxanes, however, this was not included in the model.

After purification, the biogas is converted to syngas via MR or DR. The reforming configuration determines the number of unit operations and the utility demand (see Figure 6). For MR, the simpler configuration, steam is added in the reforming reactor to reduce coking of the catalyst and to shift the syngas towards the desired stoichiometric ratio for the subsequent MeOH synthesis. For DR, CO_2 is supplied in excess at the inlet of the reforming reactor to reduce coke formation on the reforming catalyst and to enhance the CH_4 conversion. The outlet gas undergoes high-temperature and low-temperature water-gas-shift reactions (HT-WGS and LT-WGS, respectively) involving the addition of steam to shift the syngas towards the desired composition. CO_2 is separated after the WGS reactions by pressure-swing adsorption and is fed back to the reforming reactor. For each type of heating, specific combinations of catalyst support and catalyst were developed. The catalyst and its support influence the reaction kinetics, thus reactor size and product selectivity. The latter is not considered in the simulations. Moreover, the heating type influences the efficiency of the power supply and the equipment needed.

Figure 6. Proposed configurations for MR and DR to produce syngas from raw biogas.

The internal heat integration of the reforming step enables that, apart from the electrical heating of the reactor, no external heat source is required for these steps. For DR, heat may be exported in the form of steam at 170 °C. This waste heat might be used to generate electricity with an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC).

The centrepiece of the conversion, the electrically-heated reforming reactor, uses either MWH or RH for heat generation. In both cases, the catalyst support is heated directly to ensure the best possible heat transfer. For MWH, two catalyst forms were prepared: (i) extrudates containing μSiC particles homogeneously distributed within Ni/ZrO_2 , and (ii) a SiC monolith coated with a $\text{Ni/CeO}_2\text{-ZrO}_2$ catalyst. For RH, the structured support consists of a cordierite-based monolith coated with the same $\text{Ni/CeO}_2\text{-ZrO}_2$ catalyst.

The efficiencies estimated for the heating technologies at TRL 9 include heat losses in the reactor shell, transformation losses in case of RH and low-temperature heat recovery from the MW generator in case of MWH. Table 4 summarises the overall efficiencies of the respective heating technologies.

Table 4. Conservative, typical and optimistic assumptions (see Section 3.4) of RH and MWH technology efficiencies at TRL 9, including a heat loss of 10 % through the reactor shell.

	Conservative	Typical	Optimistic
RH	0.81	0.85	0.89
MWH	0.72	0.77	0.81

Renewable H_2 (“green” H_2 from electrolysis) is added to further adjust the stoichiometric ratio for MeOH synthesis, defined as $(\text{H}_2\text{-CO}_2)/(\text{CO}+\text{CO}_2)$, to about 2.1. H_2 is produced on-site by water electrolysis, with different technologies such as anion exchange membrane (AEM), proton exchange membrane (PEM) and high-temperature electrolysis by a solid oxide electrolyser cell (HTE/SOEC). The impact of H_2 production strongly depends on the electricity source used and the energy efficiency. The considered energy efficiencies range from 0.62 to 0.82 kWh H_2 produced/kWh electricity consumed [34]. The energy content of H_2 is expressed on a LHV basis. The best efficiency can only be reached with HTE/SOEC, the least mature electrolyser technology. The co-product O_2 is released to the atmosphere without valorisation. No heat integration with the rest of the ēQATOR plant is considered.

The syngas is then converted to raw MeOH in a boiler feed water reactor using a standard MeOH synthesis catalyst. The excess steam produced by the reaction is used to distil raw MeOH to a purity of 99.85 % by removing wastewater and any impurities produced during MeOH synthesis. H_2 and light hydrocarbons purged from the MeOH synthesis step could be recycled to the syngas reactor. However, this step is not included in the simulation at the current TRL of the concept development.

For the end-of-life phase, GHG emissions released into the atmosphere from combustion in waste incineration plants or during biodegradation are considered. CO_2 from ēQATOR MeOH is biogenic CO_2 whereas CO_2 from fossil-derived MeOH is fossil CO_2 , which makes a difference in the assessment. Other emissions such as nitrogen oxides (NOx) and volatile organic compounds depend on the application but are identical for the different systems. As a worst-case scenario, combustion in a waste incineration plant is considered to prevent a potentially influential life cycle stage from being overlooked.

3.2 Reference systems

Today, approximately 65 % of all MeOH is produced from natural gas and 35 % from coal [35]. Less than 1 % is produced from biomass and renewables [35]. In the future, different technologies might

be available to produce renewable MeOH. The renewable carbon sources required for this include biomass or CO₂ captured from the air, the sea or industrial exhaust gases. Numerous synthesis routes are discussed today to obtain renewable MeOH.

Consequently, the eQATOR concept is compared with these technological options.

- a) Current and future MeOH production from natural gas (henceforth referred to as “fossil MeOH”) to analyse potential savings,
- b) Synthesis routes that also supply MeOH from biogas to identify the advantages and disadvantages of the different technologies using the same biomass source, and
- c) Direct MeOH synthesis from H₂ made with renewable electricity and CO₂ from DAC as an exemplary carbon source, to assess future benefits from a reduced use biomass, a limited carbon resource.

Figure 7 illustrates the MeOH synthesis processes considered in this analysis. Sections 3.2.1 - 3.2.5 explain the processes in detail.

Figure 7. Simplified PFDs illustrating key similarities and differences between eQATOR and reference systems. Extra abbreviations in this Figure: CS (carbon storage), e⁻ (electricity).

3.2.1 Methanol from natural gas

To produce MeOH from natural gas, syngas is produced and converted into MeOH. A number of processes are available to produce syngas [35]. SMR accounts for approximately 60 % of the global production capacity of MeOH [36]. Thus, SMR will be used as a typical fossil reference process. Figure 8 shows a simplified PFD of MeOH production from natural gas via SMR.

Figure 8. PFD of MeOH production from natural gas via SMR [36].

For the SMR process, natural gas is used as a feedstock (carbon source), to provide thermal energy to the process and to generate electricity for internal use. The natural gas is desulphurised. Steam made from process water is added to generate syngas in the SMR step. The SMR steps include reforming and HT-WGS and LT-WGS reactions. The syngas is sent to the MeOH unit where it is converted to MeOH by a catalytic process generally based on a copper-zinc oxide-alumina catalyst [35]. The raw MeOH is then distilled to remove water and any impurities produced during MeOH synthesis. H₂ and light hydrocarbons purged from the MeOH synthesis step are used internally to fuel the SMR process and to produce steam [36]. Data from ecoinvent v3.11 [37] based on literature processes [36, 38, 39] were used to model the inputs and outputs of the process. To account for different plant efficiencies currently installed, the natural gas consumption was modelled according to data provided by Althaus et al. [36].

3.2.2 Methanol from natural gas with carbon capture and storage

As a possible future development, SMR can be combined with carbon capture and storage (CCS). In the conventional process described in Section 3.2.1, CO₂ emissions into the air, which arise from heating the reforming reaction by natural gas and purge gas, are reduced by capturing CO₂ using absorption with monoethanolamine (MEA). The captured CO₂ is then compressed to 11 MPa and ready for transport in pipelines to saline aquifers. The CO₂ capture and compression increases the electricity demand of the MeOH plant. Thus, the inputs and outputs of the SMR plant with CCS are the same as for the conventional SMR process except for the electricity demand and the CO₂ emissions. Data for this input and output and for the combusted fuel and purge gas are modelled according to Santos et al. [38] and Althaus et al. [36], respectively. MEA consumption is modelled according to Liebich et al. [40]. Transport of compressed CO₂ by pipeline or ship and further electricity demand for CO₂ injection and monitoring are not considered.

Further options, e.g. CH₄ cracking yielding solid carbon and H₂, subsequent storage of the carbon and MeOH synthesis from H₂ and biogenic or atmospheric CO₂ [41] were not included in the analysis. For these scenarios, substantial CCS is necessary (0.38 t C or 1.5 t CO₂/t MeOH), while the possibilities of uptake are scarce [42].

3.2.3 Methanol from biogas upgraded for use in conventional SMR plants

Biogas can be upgraded by separating CH₄ for injection into the natural gas grid while CO₂ is vented to the atmosphere. The injected CH₄ can then be used in a conventional SMR plant to produce MeOH according to the process described in described in Section 3.2.1.

Biogas upgrading technologies are readily available and already installed at numerous biogas plants. Existing infrastructure for MeOH synthesis can be used. However, roughly half of the carbon contained in the biogas (as CO₂) is not valorised but emitted and part of the CH₄ is burned to fuel the SMR process. Various technologies are available for separating CO₂ from CH₄. For this analysis, pressure-swing adsorption is used as a proxy with direct process emissions of 2 % CH₄.

3.2.4 Methanol from biogas methanation for use in conventional SMR plants

To valorise the CO₂ contained in biogas, it can be converted into CH₄ by methanation according to Eq. (1) before being fed into the natural gas grid. This CH₄ can then be used in a conventional SMR plant to produce MeOH according to the process described in described in Section 3.2.1.

Both biological and catalytic methanation processes are discussed in the literature [43, 44]. For catalytic methanation, purification of the raw biogas is necessary to avoid catalyst poisoning. The methanation reaction takes place in the gas phase. For biological methanation, appropriate microorganisms and nutrient suspensions are required. This reaction takes place in the liquid phase. Both processes take place at high pressure (approximately 16 bar) and H₂ is added in a stoichiometric ratio. The reaction is exothermic; therefore, cooling is required. The product gas needs to be dried prior to feeding into the natural gas grid. As a proxy, purification similar to the ēQATOR process and the compression of the educts to 16 bar are considered.

3.2.5 Methanol from Direct Air Capture and Carbon Utilisation

Renewable MeOH can be synthesised directly from renewable CO₂ and H₂ according to Eq. (2).

Both DAC and production of (renewable) H₂ are currently under development, so future projections must take into account a bandwidth of impacts. Different technologies are available for DAC, but, for this analysis, a low-temperature adsorption-based DAC process is considered, as it can utilise low-temperature waste heat, enabling synergy effects with MeOH synthesis [45]. H₂ can be provided by water electrolysis, as explained in Section 3.1. The co-product oxygen is vented to the atmosphere.

Energy inputs for DAC, H₂ production and MeOH synthesis are modelled according to Rosental et al. [34] and Mennitto et al. [46]. Infrastructure is derived from Rosental et al. [34, 45], Delpierre et al. [47] and Hank [48]. H₂ emissions during electrolysis and use are considered according to Mendelevitch et. al. [49].

3.3 Electricity, heating and cooling

For the analyses, European electricity production projected to 2030 and 2050 is used. Datasets from the ifeu-internal prospective LCI database 'LCAsT' [12] (see Section 2.2.3) for the normative scenario 'GreenLate' for the reference years 2030 and 2050 [17] are used. The GreenLate scenarios include electricity projections for Europe by Teske et al. [16] (2.0 °C scenario), while Germany's electricity mix was developed within the REFINE project [14]. Figure 9 shows the composition of the European electricity mix in 2030 and 2050. Renewable electricity's share of the total production is project to be 71 % by 2030 and 100 % by 2050. The carbon intensity of the electricity is 220 g CO₂/kWh in 2030 and to 18 g CO₂/kWh in 2050.

Figure 9. Share of different energy sources in total electricity production in Europe as projected for 2030 and 2050.

The LCI data for each renewable energy source includes infrastructure with emissions and resource use corresponding to the year of construction. In 2050, additional measures for grid stabilisation are included, specifically batteries and the production, storage and (re-)conversion of H₂ into electricity.

For temperatures up to 120 °C, a heat pump with a coefficient of performance (COP) of half the Carnot efficiency at an ambient temperature of 10 °C is used [50]. High temperature heat (> 800 °C) is supplied by RH with an efficiency of 0.81 to 0.89 or by MWH with an efficiency of 0.72 to 0.81, taking into account heat losses of the heating system as well as of the heated parts. As the required experimental data from the project is not available at this time, these ranges were aligned with project partners. All heat requirements at temperatures between 120 °C and 800 °C could be covered by heat integration. Cooling is modelled with an air closed-loop, an air-cooled compression cycle with a COP = 3 [51]. In case excess heat is available, an ORC process is modelled for optimistic technology development to produce electricity.

3.4 Scenarios

A scenario-based assessment is applied. Each analysed scenario represents one potential future implementation of the assessed technologies, for both ēQATOR and the reference systems. When deriving the mass and energy balances for these generic scenarios, data obtained from project experiments, databases and literature are considered and used to extrapolate to mature technology for 2030. Uncertainty and future freedom of choice are covered by applying value ranges from ‘conservative’ to ‘typical’ to ‘optimistic’. Each scenario represents a complete life cycle from cradle to grave, i.e. one specific combination of options for each processing step.

All possible combinations of the ēQATOR scenarios are shown in Figure 10. Simulation data are only

Figure 10. Overview of possible ēQATOR scenarios. Abbreviations: AD (anaerobic digestion).

available for two of the four possible combinations of feedstock and reforming configuration, marked with a green dotted frame in Figure 10. The previous feedstock use is explained in detail in Section 3.1. Table 5 shows all ēQATOR and reference scenarios analysed.

Table 5. Overview of assessed ēQATOR and reference scenarios. All scenarios were analysed for different technology development. For systems involving the use of biogas, the impact of biogas was considered in scenarios A and B, accounting for the previous feedstock use (compare Section 3.1).

Scenario	Carbon source	Configuration	Heating system
ēQATOR: OF-MSW – DR – RH ^a	OF-MSW	DR	RH
ēQATOR: OF-MSW – DR – MWH	OF-MSW	DR	MWH
ēQATOR: Manure – MR – RH	Manure	MR	RH
ēQATOR: Manure – MR – MWH	Manure	MR	MWH
Fossil: Natural gas – SMR	Natural gas	SMR	Combustion of natural gas
Fossil: Natural gas – SMR including CCS	Natural gas	SMR	Combustion of natural gas with CCS
Synthetic: CO ₂ + H ₂	Air	Direct synthesis from CO ₂ and H ₂	Electricity
Biobased: biogas-upgrading + SMR	CH ₄ from OF-MSW	Biogas upgrading, injection into CH ₄ grid, SMR	Combustion of biomethane
Hybrid: biomethanation + SMR	CH ₄ and CO ₂ from OF-MSW	Biogas methanation, injection into CH ₄ grid, SMR	Combustion of biomethane

^a ēQATOR base case.

4 Results

A screening LCA and a GHG balance according to the RED were carried out for MeOH production from biogas by electrically heated DR or MR (ēQATOR concept). The underlying LCI data are intended to represent the process at TRL 9 in 2030. Different variants of this production route are compared to each other, conventional fossil MeOH and, in case of LCA, alternative production routes for renewable MeOH. For details on the methods and analysed systems, see Sections 2 and 3, respectively. First, an overview of the ēQATOR concept is given in Section 4.1. Second, the variants of this concept are compared with MeOH production from natural gas in Section 4.2 and with future MeOH production from biogas, electricity or natural gas in Section 4.3. All scenarios are compared and put into the context of resource availability in Section 4.4. Third, the possible applicability of ēQATOR MeOH based on the GHG balance according to the RED framework, is in Section 4.5. KPIs defined in the project are evaluated in Section 4.6.

4.1 The ēQATOR concept and its variants

4.1.1 Base case

In a first step, the environmental impacts in the impact category ‘climate change’ are analysed for the base case scenario, specifically the production of MeOH with biogas from OF-MSW and using the DR process driven by RH (OF-MSW – DR – RH). The biogas is set to be diverted from its current use in a CHP unit (compare scenario A in Section 3.1). This forgone use is replaced by heat and power provision from a European electricity mix projected for 2030. Figure 11 shows the life cycle GHG emissions (GWP indicator) of MeOH as CO₂-eq/t MeOH.

As can be seen from Figure 11, the production and end-of-life of ēQATOR MeOH in the year 2030 is associated with the emission of 1.6 t CO₂-eq/t MeOH (net result shown as thin white bar in

Figure 11. Life cycle GHG emissions in 2030 of ēQATOR MeOH for the base case of OF-MSW – DR – RH. The biogas is set to be diverted from its current use in a CHP plant (scenario A) whose products need to be replaced. **How to read the figure:** The coloured sections of the thick bar relate to specific life cycle stages or process steps of MeOH from cradle-to-gate, except the use phase. The white thin bar reflects the net result combining emissions and credits.

Figure 11), or, considering a LHV of 19.9 MJ/kg for MeOH, to approximately 80 g CO₂-eq/MJ fuel. CO₂ contributes to more than 90 % of all GHG emissions, mainly from electricity production, which is still expected to be based on a 25 % share of natural gas, hard coal and lignite in 2030.

In the next step, the environmental impacts of the ēQATOR base case scenario are analysed for all impact categories, as shown in Figure 12. While in Figure 11 the results for the indicator GWP are expressed in t CO₂-eq, these results are normalised in Figure 12 to IEs to make impact categories comparable. The impact categories, the corresponding LCIA methods, indicators and normalisation factors are explained in detail in Section 2.2.4.

Regarding these other environmental impacts, the indicator NREU sticks out with 840 IE/1000 t MeOH due to the fossil shares in the electricity production. The indicators GWP, AP, TEP and PM are in the midfield at roughly 180 – 280 IE/1000 t MeOH. The ODP and LU indicators correspond to less than 80 IE/1000 t MeOH.

Key findings:

- In 2030, MeOH produced via the ēQATOR concept is expected to have a GWP of 1.6 t CO₂-eq/t MeOH – or 80 g CO₂-eq/MJ fuel – based on a European electricity mix.
- When normalised to European per-capita reference values, NREU reaches the highest normalised value, followed by GWP, AP, TEP and PM.

4.1.2 Hotspot analysis

To answer the question which life cycle stages and process steps contribute most to the environmental impact, Figure 13 shows the relative contributions (in %) of in the individual environmental impact categories for the base case of OF-MSW – DR – RH with scenario A as expected for the year 2030 (left). This format is chosen because, when normalised to IEs, the contributions of life cycle stages with relative insignificance compared to other indicators are difficult to assess. Additionally, this scenario was evaluated for a fully renewable European electricity mix for 2050 (right). Since the results for the base case scenario are similar to those for the other three ēQATOR scenarios investigated, the latter are not depicted.

In 2030, biogas, electricity for heating the reforming reactor, electricity for the production of H₂ and electricity for gas compression (light green, orange, blue and purple bars, respectively, in Figure 13) contribute the most to the environmental impact in all investigated impact categories. In addition, emissions attributed to the end-of-life phase – here modelled as a worst-case-scenario, combustion

Figure 12. Life cycle environmental impacts normalised to inhabitant equivalents of ēQATOR MeOH the base case OF-MSW – DR – RH. The biogas is set to be diverted from its current use in a CHP plant (scenario A) whose products need to be replaced. **How to read the figure:** The coloured sections of the thick bar relate to specific life cycle stages or process steps of MeOH from cradle-to-gate except the use phase. The white thin bar reflects the net result combining emissions and credits. Different bars reflect different environmental impact categories. LCIA methods and normalisation are explained in detail in Section 2.2.4.

in a waste incineration plant – make a significant contribution in the impact categories AP, TEP and PMF. Other materials (e.g., adsorbents for biogas purification), infrastructure and direct emissions play a minor role. Impacts from the catalyst and wastewater are negligible.

In 2050, with a more environmentally friendly electricity mix, the relative contribution of infrastructure, direct emissions and end-of-life emissions grow with respect to electricity-related contributions. For the impact category GWP, the avoided emissions dominate the system. These are basically connected to CH₄ emissions from a biogas-fuelled CHP plant, which are avoided by diverting the biogas to ēQATOR instead. It is debatable whether this credit may be given in 2050, since CHP technology may have evolved by then.

In a further step, Figure 14 shows the net results normalised to IE/t MeOH produced with the ēQATOR base case OF-MSW – DR – RH in 2030 (left) and in 2050 (right). This way, the relative importance of each impact can be evaluated. By relating the environmental impacts to the corresponding average per-capita values for Europe and applying European electricity mixes projected for 2030 and 2050, it can be concluded that changes in the background system – most notably the electricity mix – successfully reduce NREU and GWP. In contrast, AP, TEP, PMF, and LU

remain critical and require further attention.

Figure 13. Relative contributions of emissions and resource uses associated with the individual process steps to the overall environmental impacts of ēQATOR MeOH (base case, scenario A) in each environmental impact category for 2030 (left) and 2050 (right). **How to read the figure:** The blue section of the top bar in the left diagram indicates that the electricity for reactor heating causes ca. 25% of the overall GHG emissions (indicator GWP) in 2030.

Figure 14. Normalised environmental impacts of ēQATOR MeOH (base case, scenario A) for 2030 (left) and 2050 (right). **How to read the figure:** The top bar in the left diagram indicates that the GHG emissions related to the production of 1 t MeOH in 2030 (base case scenario) corresponds to approximately 20 % of the GHG emissions one average EU citizen emitted in the year 2010. LCIA methods and normalisation are explained in detail in Section 2.2.4.

In conjunction with Figure 13, the results show that further reductions in end-of-life emissions are

particularly important for TEP and PMF. For the impact category LU, impacts should be mitigated by minimising the LU of renewable electricity generation, for example by reducing the use of woody biomass for power production. For AP, both lower end-of-life emissions and a reduced AP of the electricity mix are required. In this context, H₂S emissions from deep geothermal power plants should be addressed through appropriate capture and utilisation. Water use, which is excluded from the study due to limited data availability and quality, may also be a relevant factor depending on the location of an ēQATOR plant.

Key findings:

- Electricity input dominates the results for 2030 while in 2050, infrastructure, direct emissions and potentially end-of-life emissions gain importance. Relative contributions of individual process steps vary across environmental impact categories.
- An increasing share of renewable electricity in the electricity mix reduces the impact categories NREU and GWP for ēQATOR MeOH, whereas AP, TEP, PMF, and LU require further mitigation.

4.1.3 Influence of heating technology

Figure 15 shows the results in the impact category ‘climate change’ for the four investigated ēQATOR scenarios for a European electricity mix, consumables and infrastructure in 2030 (left) and 2050 (right), comparing the different heating technologies of RH and MWH for both the MR of biogas from manure and the DR of biogas from OF-MSW.

Figure 15. Life cycle GHG emissions from ēQATOR MeOH for different scenarios comparing RH and MWH for 2030 (left) and 2050 (right). **How to read the figure:** See Figure 11.

To analyse the impact of the heating technology, scenarios with the same reforming technology (MR or DR) and the same biogas feedstock (manure or OF-MSW) are compared. Figure 15 demonstrates that the effect of heating technology on the environmental impact is small in 2030 (with MWH having a slightly higher impact than RH). By 2050, with fully renewable energy, the influence of the heating technology on the impact category ‘climate change’ is even lower than in 2030. The reasons are that the differences in overall efficiency, including heat losses, are small; the overall efficiency of RH at TRL 9 is expected to be 85 %, while the overall efficiency of MWH is expected to be 77 % for

typical technology development (compare Section 3.1). Moreover, reactor heating (orange bars in Figure 15) contributes only a small fraction to the overall environmental impact. Additionally, the differing complexity of the infrastructure (pink bars in Figure 15), which is higher for MWH, has no significant effect on the overall environmental impact in 2050. Consequently, ēQATOR scenarios involving RH and MWH differ only slightly due to the differences in predicted efficiencies. These findings are also transferable to other environmental impact categories (see the analysis of LU, the impact category most sensitive to heating technology in Figure A4, Appendix).

Key findings:

- The choice of heating technology on the overall environmental impact of ēQATOR MeOH is small in 2030 and negligible in 2050 for all environmental impact categories investigated. The main reason for any differences is the different overall efficiencies predicted for TRL 9 plants.

4.1.4 Influence of reforming configuration and biogas feedstock

In addition to the heating configurations, the two reforming configurations DR and MR and the two biogas feedstocks, OF-MSW and manure, were assessed. Figure 16 compares the effect of these factors, which were not analysed separately, for RH in the impact category ‘climate change’, assuming that biogas would otherwise be used in a CHP unit (scenario A). Table 6 summarises the key differences between the two scenarios shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Life cycle GHG emissions of ēQATOR MeOH for different scenarios comparing different biogas feedstocks (OF-MSW and manure) and reforming types (DR and MR) for 2030 (left) and 2050 (right). The biogas is set to be diverted from its current use in a CHP plant (scenario A). **How to read the figure:** See Figure 11.

The analysis in Table 6 shows that the three life cycle stages ‘CHP: avoided emissions’, ‘CHP: forgone credits’ and ‘Electricity: H₂ provision’ have complementary but inseparable attributes upon a change in reforming configuration and biogas feedstock, while the life cycle stage ‘Electricity: Reactor heating’ has opposing and inseparable attributes. While two of the four scenarios were not part of the process simulation, it is expected that the emissions of those involving manure will be greater than those using OF-MSW, when using the same heating technology and reforming configuration.

By 2030, the scenario “manure – MR” has slight advantages over the scenario “OF-MSW – DR”. By 2050, this advantage diminishes due to a higher relative impact of direct H₂ emissions compared to the impact of the electricity provision. Recall that the GWP₁₀₀ of H₂ is still under discussion, see Section 2.2.4. Since the impact of H₂ emissions depend on the amount of atmospheric CH₄, tropospheric ozone and stratospheric vapor vapour concentrations, predictions for 2050 are even

Table 6. Key differences between the scenarios “OF-MSW – DR – RH – A” and “manure – MR – RH – A”. Values in parenthesis are related to results for each life cycle stage.

Life cycle stage	Disadvantageous configuration	Reason(s)
CHP: Avoided emissions	Manure – MR	MR leads to higher carbon efficiency → lower biogas demand (< -4 %). Biogas from manure has lower CH ₄ content/LHV → fewer avoided emissions/m ³ biogas (-9 %) from CHP (effects have the same general trend but are not clearly separable)
CHP: Forgone credits	OF-MSW – DR	DR leads to lower carbon efficiency → higher biogas demand (> +4 %). Biogas from OF-MSW has higher CH ₄ content/LHV → more avoided emissions from CHP electricity production/m ³ biogas (+9 %) (effects have the same general trend but are not clearly separable)
Electricity: Reactor heating	OF-MSW – DR	DR requires CO ₂ recycle → more energy required at highest temperature (> + 40 %). Biogas from OF-MSW has higher CH ₄ content → lower H ₂ or reactor heating demand (opposing effects and not clearly separable)
Electricity: H₂ provision	Manure – MR	MR has no HT- and LT-WGS, possibly H ₂ O not optimally used for internal H ₂ formation → higher H ₂ demand. Biogas from manure has lower CH ₄ content → higher H ₂ or reactor heating demand (effects have the same general trend but are not clearly separable)
Electricity: Others	OF-MSW – DR	DR requires CO ₂ recycle and separation → additional compression work
Infrastructure	OF-MSW – DR	DR requires additional reaction units and CO ₂ recycle / separation → more infrastructure
Direct emissions	Manure – MR	Higher H ₂ demand → higher direct emissions from H ₂ provision

less robust. However, it can be concluded that the differences in environmental impacts of the different reforming configurations are expected to be negligible with minimal advantages for MR. The use of biogas with a high CH₄ content is slightly favourable if biogas would otherwise be used in a CHP unit.

In contrast to scenario A, where biogas is diverted from its current use in a CHP plant, manure or OF-MSW are not exploited to produce biogas prior to the installation of ēQATOR in scenario B. Figure 17 clearly illustrates the substantial impact of different biogas feedstocks both by 2030 and by 2050 in this case. While emissions and credits associated with biogas from OF-MSW are similar in magnitude, the credits attributed to manure-based biogas far exceed its emissions. This results from the significantly lower emissions (and thus avoided environmental burdens) of biogas digestate applied to fields compared to the application of raw manure. These differences are considerably larger than those arising from the choice of reforming configuration. It should be noted that these findings cannot be extrapolated to biogas from dedicated energy crops or to situations involving additional livestock or additional organic waste generation.

Key findings:

- Differences in environmental impacts between the different reforming configurations are expected to be negligible with minimal advantages for MR.
- The use of biogas with a high CH₄ content is slightly favourable if biogas is diverted from its current use in a CHP unit.
- If previously undigested manure or OF-MSW is anaerobically digested and used for MeOH

production as a consequence of the installation of ēQATOR, biogas from this manure receives high credits due to the avoidance of environmental burdens. These credits are higher than those for biogas from OF-MSW.

Figure 17. Life cycle GHG emissions of ēQATOR MeOH, comparing different biogas feedstocks (OF-MSW and manure) and reforming types (DR and MR), assuming that biogas feedstock has not been used before (scenario B) for 2030 (left) and 2050 (right).

4.1.5 Technology development and optimisation potential

The ēQATOR processes are currently at immature TRL, mainly TRLs 5 and 6. However, this LCA is conducted for scenarios representing mature technology on industrial scale ('nth plant'), as explained in Section 2.1.2. To accommodate for possible optimisation potentials from future technological developments, an analysis of the impact of future development ranging from 'optimistic' via 'typical' to 'conservative' has been done. Figure 18 illustrates the LCA results for MeOH produced by the

Figure 18. Life cycle GHG emissions and credits of ēQATOR MeOH for the ēQATOR base case scenario applying 'conservative' via 'typical' to 'optimistic' for 2030 (left) and 2050 (right). **How to read the figure:** The 2nd bar on the left-hand side corresponds to the base case scenario as shown in Figure 11 with life-cycle stage contributions and net LCA results (white bar). The bottom bar reflects the range of net results from 'optimistic' (left end of the bar), 'typical' (central marker), and 'optimistic' values (right end of the bar).

OF-MSW – DR – RH base case for the impact category ‘climate change’ for a European electricity mix in 2030 (left) and 2050 (right) and if biogas was already used in a CHP (scenario A). The typical and conservative technology development scenarios assume the same level of heat integration, which is already sophisticated and was developed during the ēQATOR project.

By 2030, the life cycle stages with the largest relative change and thus optimisation potential in the impact category ‘climate change’ are the direct emissions and the electricity demand for reactor heating, the H₂ provision and others. The efficiency of the electricity-to-heat conversion, the choice of technology for the H₂ provision, the utilisation of low temperature waste heat and the use of the C1/C2 co-products from the MeOH synthesis step are the key parameters. By 2050 with the use of fully renewable electricity, infrastructure and direct emissions are levers for further optimisation. The absolute GHG emissions attributed to the ēQATOR system also depend on the emissions avoided by not burning the biogas in a CHP plant, which could also be optimised.

To analyse whether these results are transferable to other impact categories, which additional optimisation potentials can be obtained by using different biogas feedstocks, reforming processes and heating technologies and how a change from a European electricity mix in 2030 to fully renewable electricity in 2050 influences the LCA results in selected environmental impact categories, the ranges of the net results are shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19 shows that technological development can substantially reduce environmental impacts in 2030, particularly for NREU, GWP, AP and PMF. In contrast, with fully renewable energy in 2050, the influence of technology development becomes negligible. Furthermore, the improvements achieved through process optimisation are far smaller than the changes induced by the background system, particularly for GHG emissions associated with electricity (and subsequent heat) generation.

Nevertheless, because renewable energy remains a limited resource (see Section 4.4.3) and residual GHG emissions must be offset through CCS, increasing electricity efficiency and reducing direct emissions remain important goals when economically feasible. Beyond the optimisation potential identified for individual scenarios, the comparison of all ēQATOR scenarios indicates that biogas with a high CH₄ content is generally the preferred feedstock.

Key findings:

- The key optimisation potential lies in the background system, i.e. type of electricity used.
- Electricity demand can be further be reduced by optimising the heating efficiency, H₂ provision, heat integration and CH₄ content of the biogas.
- When abundant renewable energy resources are available, further optimisation should focus on direct process emissions and end-of-life emissions.

4.2 Comparison with fossil methanol production (2030)

When comparing the ēQATOR concept with the fossil reference system – SMR of natural gas – feedstock, capacity and heating technology change. While a fossil MeOH plant yields 3 000 to 5 000 t MeOH/d (with an upward trend) [52, 53], a mature ēQATOR plant would yield roughly 14 t MeOH/d. The heating technology changes from natural gas-fired thermal heating to electric heating. Figure 20 compares the LCA results of these two technologies.

Figure 20 shows that by 2030, MeOH produced in the base case ēQATOR scenario already exhibits lower NREU and lower GWP than fossil MeOH. For fossil MeOH, NREU is largely driven by natural gas use, both as an energy carrier and as a feedstock. Its GWP is dominated by end-of-life GHG emissions released when MeOH or downstream products are combusted or degraded. Capacity changes and the resulting additional infrastructure required for ēQATOR do not affect the results. For all other

Figure 19. Ranges of net results in selected environmental impact categories for MeOH production and end-of-life treatment in 2030 and 2050 across different ēQATOR scenarios, comparing biogas feedstocks (OF-MSW and manure), reforming configurations (DR and MR) and heating technologies (MWH and RH). Biogas is set to be diverted from its current use in a CHP unit (scenario A). **How to read the figure:** The top bar describes the GWP of the ēQATOR base case scenario for three assumptions on technology development: ‘optimistic’ (left end of the bar), ‘typical’ (central marker), and ‘conservative’ (right end of the bar). This bar corresponds to the range shown in Figure 18 (left). Arrows indicate a substantial reduction in environmental impact resulting from changes in the background system.

Figure 20. Life cycle environmental impacts normalised to IE, comparing the ēQATOR base case – with biogas set to be diverted from its use in a CHP unit (scenario A) – with conventional SMR. **How to read the figure:** The first bar corresponds to the ēQATOR base case scenario as in Figure 11. indicators, the fossil reference remains advantageous over ēQATOR.

Key findings:

- By 2030, ēQATOR already offers advantages over MeOH from SMR in NREU and GWP.
- Disadvantages are observed in all other impact categories.

4.3 Comparison with future methanol production (2050)

In 2050, the production of MeOH from natural gas might be improved by applying CCS for all CO₂ emissions and using renewable electricity for auxiliaries. Figure 21 thus compares the LCA results of the ēQATOR base case scenario with fossil MeOH production (SMR from natural gas) including these improvements. Moreover, other renewable technologies might become available to produce MeOH. These biogas-based, synthetic and hybrid scenarios are described in detail in Section 3.2.3 to 3.2.5. Figure 21 shows ranges of results of due to technology development from ‘conservative’ via ‘typical’ to ‘optimistic’.

Figure 21 shows that the ēQATOR base case scenario (and all others) using a European electricity mix in 2050 outperforms future low-carbon fossil MeOH production in terms of NREU, GWP and PMF.

Figure 21. Ranges of LCA results in key environmental impact categories for MeOH for the ēQATOR base case and future reference scenarios in 2050, with biogas set to be diverted from its current use in a CHP unit (scenario A). **How to read the figure:** Values are normalised to IE as explained in Section 2.2.4. The top bar reflects the range of net results from ‘optimistic’ (left end of the bar), ‘typical’ (central marker), and ‘conservative’ values (right end of the bar) for GHG emissions associated with the ēQATOR base case as shown in Figure 18. The bar for NREU of fossil MeOH is not shown to scale for clarity since it far exceeds other values.

Similar impacts are expected for TEP. The slight disadvantage of ēQATOR in AP is expected to disappear since it is basically due to the high H₂S emissions from deep geothermal power plants. These specific emissions are expected to be reduced. However, this improvement is not yet included in the prospective LCI database used. The only disadvantages of ēQATOR compared to fossil scenario is for LU. This disadvantage can be reduced by considerate roll-out of renewable energy. For example, biofuels and bioenergy require far more land than solar and wind power for the same amount of energy [54]. Specific LU and environmental damage can further be improved and mitigated by synergy effects, e.g. by installing agri-photovoltaics.

Comparing the ēQATOR base case scenario to other pathways for producing renewable MeOH, similar impacts are expected for these other hybrid pathways (biogas methanation and subsequent SMR in an existing conventional plant, see Section 3.2.4). Except for GWP, environmental impacts for biogas upgrading and subsequent SMR in an existing plant are smaller than for the ēQATOR scenario. The GWP associated with biogas upgrading and subsequent SMR in an existing plant largely depends on the direct CH₄ emissions of this process. Compared to synthetic MeOH from atmospheric CO₂ and H₂ from water electrolysis, ēQATOR offers environmental advantages in all selected impact categories. However, there are still overall advantages of this synthetic MeOH compared to low-carbon fossil MeOH (with impacts in ‘acidification’ having a huge potential to be reduced).

To contextualise the presented scenarios in terms of their technical performance and resource requirements, Figure 22 shows the demand for biogas (or natural gas in the case of fossil MeOH), assessed using LHV, as well as the demand for renewable electricity. Compared with SMR for fossil MeOH production, all biogenic and synthetic pathways require slightly more energy from input materials. This is plausible, as additional effort is required either for separating CO₂ and CH₄ (bio-based pathway) or for separating CO₂ from air (synthetic pathway). An overall efficiency like that for fossil MeOH can be achieved, for example, via the synthetic pathway. However, this is currently possible only with high-temperature electrolysis, which is presently at TRL 7–8 [55]. In the ēQATOR base case scenario, the choice of reforming configuration (MR instead of DR as for the base case) can further increase efficiency. In summary, it can be concluded that, irrespective of the pathway, approximately 1.5 MJ – 2 MJ of either biogas or renewable electricity are required per MJ MeOH produced. This is in line with the IRENA estimate of 1.6 MJ – 1.9 MJ of biomass per MJ MeOH necessary for MeOH production from biomass gasification [35].

Figure 22. Biogas/natural gas and electricity input for MeOH produced with different pathways for ‘conservative’ (top bar for each pathway) to ‘typical’ (middle bar) to ‘optimistic’ (bottom bar) technology development for emerging technologies and fossil MeOH production with CCS. The grey shaded area corresponds to efficiencies reached by conventional fossil MeOH production.

Key findings:

- By 2050, ēQATOR is clearly environmentally favourable compared to fossil MeOH and slightly more favourable than synthetic MeOH (CO₂ from DAC and H₂ from electrolysis)
- By 2050, the environmental performance of ēQATOR is similar to other hybrid pathways.

- By 2050, biogas upgrading and subsequent SMR outperforms ēQATOR pathways for all investigated environmental impact categories except GWP, however, at the cost of high biogenic carbon use.
- The production of 1 MJ of MeOH requires 1.5 MJ to 2 MJ of biogas or electricity.

4.4 Future methanol demand and resource availability

To contextualise the LCA results and derive consistent recommendations, it is essential to consider future MeOH demand and resource availability, as LCA assesses environmental impacts only per kg MeOH. Consequently, the environmentally most favourable pathway may be feasible only for a limited share of total MeOH production, thereby constraining system-wide optimisation from an environmental perspective. For this reason, future MeOH demand and the availability of biogas from sustainable feedstocks, as well as renewable electricity, are reviewed and compared.

4.4.1 Future methanol demand

In 2024, global MeOH production amounted to 112 million t. If current trends continue, production could increase to around 500 million t annually by 2050 [35]. This corresponds to approximately 2.2 EJ (1 exajoule = 10^{18} J) in 2024 and potentially up to 10 EJ in 2050.

At present, MeOH is used either as a precursor for chemical derivatives or as a fuel. Major derivatives include formaldehyde, polyethylene, polypropylene and acetic acid. These chemicals are processed subsequently into a wide range of consumer products, such as insulation and packaging materials, detergents, adhesives and solvents, which serve diverse applications. As a fuel, MeOH can be used directly, blended with petrol, used for trans-esterification of vegetable oils into biodiesel fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) or converted into methyl tert-butyl ether (MTBE) or dimethyl ether (DME) [35].

Looking ahead, the growing demand for renewable fuels for ships and the broader need to defossilise the chemical industry, particularly plastics, are expected to further increase the global MeOH consumption [56]. Moreover, the demand for plastic in food packaging and online retail is currently increasing [57, 58].

4.4.2 Resource demand

To provide the current MeOH demand, this study concludes that 3.4 EJ – 4.4 EJ biogas and/or renewable electricity are necessary. By 2050, 15 EJ – 20 EJ biogas and renewable electricity would be necessary globally to meet the expected MeOH demand.

4.4.3 Resource availability and exploitability

Renewable electricity

In 2023, global consumption of renewable electricity (including 7 % transmission losses) reached 30 EJ, accounting for around 30 % of total electricity use. The total renewable energy consumption – covering electricity, heat, and transport – amounted to 60 EJ [59], or approximately 13 % of global energy consumption. In the same year, 565 GW of new renewable final electricity capacity were installed, bringing the total global capacity to about 2 000 GW, with annual additions continuing to increase.

The International Energy Agency projects that global renewable electricity capacity will exceed 5 500 GW by 2030 [59], equivalent to roughly 95 EJ of global renewable final energy consumption, or around 20 % of the total final energy consumption. If global MeOH production was maintained at 2024 levels and supplied entirely by electricity, roughly 4 % of global renewable electricity generation would be required. However, as total energy demand will not be fully met by renewables in 2030, significant competition for renewable electricity is expected. Reliable projections beyond 2030, particularly towards 2050, are currently not available.

Biogas

In 2023, global biogas consumption amounted to 1.7 EJ, primarily used for electricity and heat generation [59]. The main producing regions were Europe (50 %) – with especially Germany accounting for about 20 % – and China (23 %). While biogas production in China and many other regions relies mainly on agricultural residues and organic wastes, roughly 25 % of biogas in Europe is derived from energy crops [60]. Energy crops have a substantially worse land use efficiency than other renewable electricity such as solar or wind power and have further negative environmental implications [54], highlighting the need to shift production towards more sustainable sources.

Biogas production is expected increase moderately to 2.3 EJ by 2030 [59]. By 2050, biogas production might increase to more than 10 EJ [59, 60]. Consequently, biogas is expected to make only a limited contribution to meeting global MeOH demand. Especially with substantial growth in MeOH production, the gap between available biogas resources and the energy required for large-scale MeOH synthesis remains considerable. A comprehensive assessment of global biomass potentials for MeOH production from both biogenic and synthetic pathways would therefore be highly valuable.

Key findings:

- Biogas from sustainable resources can only contribute to a part of renewable MeOH supply.
- Renewable electricity is also a limited resource, so optimised pathways need to be considered.
- Hybrid pathways and synthetic pathways together have a good potential to defossilise MeOH production if this production is not substantially increased.
- Other sustainable resources such as solid biomass need to be considered as well.

4.5 GHG balances according to the RED

ēQATOR MeOH can be classified partly as an advanced biofuel and partly as a RFNBO. Figure 23

Figure 23. GHG emissions calculated in accordance with the rules defined in the RED applicable from 2025, shown as a function of the electricity emission intensity. **How to read the figure:** The y-intercepts of the dotted lines represent the emissions or credits associated with the biogas provision, transport and materials of the respective scenario. The dotted lines represent the GHG emissions of ēQATOR MeOH as a function of the electricity’s emission intensity. Their intersection with the green line (blue circles) indicates the maximum GHG intensity that still meets the sustainability criteria of the RED.

illustrates the GHG emissions and credits of MeOH produced with the ēQATOR concepts, the fossil fuel comparator for transport (94 g CO₂-eq/MJ fuel) and the corresponding threshold for ēQATOR fuels accounting for the respective share of advanced biofuel and RFNBO (about 32 g CO₂-eq/MJ fuel). Calculation methods are detailed in Section 2.3.

Figure 23 illustrates that, when biogas from manure is used for MeOH production, the required GHG savings relative to the fossil fuel comparator can be achieved at electricity GHG intensities below approximately 400 g CO₂-eq/kWh. When biogas from the OF-MSW is used, the electricity GHG intensity must be below about 100 g CO₂-eq/kWh. This difference arises from the additional credits attributed to manure-based biogas according to the RED.

For comparison, in 2020 the RED compatible GHG intensity of electricity in European countries ranged from 14.8 g CO₂-eq/kWh in Sweden to more than 700 g CO₂-eq/kWh in Cyprus [33]. Consequently, ēQATOR MeOH can already meet the sustainability criteria in several European countries. Notably, in addition to meeting these thresholds, the electricity used for the RFNBO share must be fully renewable to qualify.

Key findings:

- ēQATOR MeOH can be classified partly as an advanced biofuel and partly as RFNBO.
- The GHG emission savings required by the RED (compared to the fossil fuel comparator) can already be met in several European countries.

4.6 KPIs related to environment

In this section, the KPIs, as defined in Section 2.1.1, are evaluated and discussed.

Zero direct local emissions from heat

The ēQATOR technology has zero direct local emissions from heat, as all thermal energy required by the system, including the heat demand of the biogas fermenter and downstream MeOH processing, is supplied electrically. As a result, no GHGs or other pollutants such as NO_x or SO₂ are released on-site from heating, provided the ēQATOR concept is implemented as intended. Consequently, this KPI is fulfilled.

Reduction in CO₂ footprint/GHG emissions

Figure 24 compares the CO₂ footprint as a measure of GHG emissions of the ēQATOR pathways to the production of fossil MeOH by SMR. The ranges displayed account for different technology development, heating technologies, reforming configurations and feedstock types for the ēQATOR pathways and for different efficiencies for the reference scenario. Scenario A refers to the case that biogas is already used in a CHP plant prior to ēQATOR installation (“alternative biogas use”), in scenario B, biogas feedstocks are newly exploited for MeOH production (“alternative biomass use”).

An emissions reduction of at least 60 % on the projected EU 2030 mix can only be reached if biogas is not exploited before (scenario B) and if manure is used as a feedstock (see Section 4.1.4). For certain renewable energy sources, e.g. off-shore wind projected to 2050, an emissions reduction of 91 % can be reached easily. This KPI might only be missed by a narrow margin in the case of conservative technology development and an unfavourable combination of process and feedstock.

Key findings:

- All KPIs can be achieved by specific ēQATOR scenarios.

5 Key findings, conclusions and recommendations

The aim of this screening-type prospective LCA is to determine to what extent and under which

Figure 24. Reduction in GHG emissions by ēQATOR concepts compared to a fossil SMR reference scenario (including electricity sources) for a projected 2030 EU electricity mix and for off-shore wind projected in 2050 (without grid stabilisation). The SMR plant is set to operate with the same electricity mix. **How to read the figure:** The arrows and associated values correspond to the emission reduction compared to the minimum or maximum emissions of fossil MeOH production.

conditions the ēQATOR concept can contribute to a more sustainable supply of MeOH. The assessment was conducted largely in accordance with the ISO 14040/44 framework, applying a cradle-to-grave system boundary. The environmental impact categories NREU, GWP, AP, TEP, ODP, PMF and LU were evaluated. Although potentially relevant, ‘water use’ was excluded from the analysis due to limited data availability at the low TRL level of the project. Two points in the future were examined, 2030 and 2050. In both cases, an average European electricity mix as forecasted by Teske et al. [16] for the respective year was used as a basis. Consumables and infrastructure are also manufactured in the corresponding year.

In addition, a GHG balance was calculated according to the calculation rules of the RED for the ēQATOR scenarios to show whether the produced MeOH could be counted towards certain European renewable energy and/or emission reduction targets. The optional LC-EIA was skipped due to the nature of the biomass feedstocks (residues and waste) and the absence of relevant *additional* local environmental impacts, especially if biogas use is simply changed.

The key findings derived from these analyses are presented in Section 5.1, the conclusions drawn from them are discussed in Section 5.2, and Section 5.3 provides recommendations for relevant stakeholder groups.

5.1 Key findings

ēQATOR base case

In 2030, based on a European electricity mix with a carbon intensity of 220 g/kWh, MeOH produced according to the ēQATOR base case scenario, OF-MSW – DR – RH is associated with a carbon footprint of approximately 1.6 t CO₂-eq/t MeOH, corresponding to about 80 g CO₂-eq/MJ fuel. When the analysed impact categories are normalised to European per-capita reference values, NREU reaches the highest normalised value, followed by GWP, AP, TEP potential and PMF.

ēQATOR hotspots

In 2030, the electricity input dominates the environmental impacts. By contrast, in 2050 – based on fully renewable electricity – impacts from infrastructure, direct emissions, and potentially end-of-life emissions become comparable to those from electricity. Moreover, the relative contributions of individual process steps vary across environmental impact categories. While an increasing share of renewable electricity in the electricity mix substantially reduces NREU and GWP, additional mitigation measures are required for AP, TEP, PMF and LU.

Comparison of different ēQATOR scenarios

In 2030, the choice of heating technology only has a minor effect on the overall environmental impacts of ēQATOR MeOH, becoming almost negligible in 2050. Differences between reforming configurations are similarly small, with only slight advantages for MR. Regarding biogas feedstock, biogas with higher CH₄ content is slightly favourable if the biogas is diverted from an existing CHP unit, while manure-based biogas provides higher environmental credits compared to biogas from OF-MSW when the feedstock is previously unexploited for energy production.

Optimisation potentials of ēQATOR scenarios

The ēQATOR concept has been iteratively optimised by reducing heat demand through heat integration and recovering compression energy. Already at this stage, it provides clear environmental benefits compared with fossil MeOH. The main remaining optimisation potential lies in the background system, i.e. the electricity type. Smaller improvements – particularly when electricity is not yet fully renewable - can be achieved by optimising the heating efficiency, the H₂ provision and the heat integration and increasing the biogas CH₄ content. When renewable energy is abundant, further optimisation should target the reduction of direct CH₄ and H₂ emissions as well as end-of-life emissions.

Comparison of ēQATOR to fossil reference scenarios

By 2030, ēQATOR already offers advantages over MeOH from SMR in NREU and GWP while disadvantages are observed in all other impact categories. By 2050, ēQATOR is clearly environmentally favourable, even with the reduction in GWP of fossil MeOH production through capture and storage of the CO₂ emissions produced by SMR.

Comparison of ēQATOR to renewable reference scenarios

By 2050, the environmental impacts of ēQATOR MeOH are slightly lower than those of synthetic MeOH (CO₂ from DAC and H₂ from electrolysis), are comparable to those of other hybrid pathways and are mostly larger than those of biogas upgrading and subsequent SMR. The production of 1 MJ MeOH requires approximately 1.5 MJ – 2 MJ of biogas or electricity regardless of the pathway.

Availability of renewable resources vs. future MeOH demand

In 2024, the global MeOH demand was 2.2 EJ, projected to reach 10 EJ by 2050. Producing this amount of MeOH requires roughly 1.5–2 times this energy in biogas or electricity. Global biogas production, 1.7 EJ in 2023 and expected to rise to 2.3 EJ by 2030, cannot meet this demand. Moreover, much of today's biogas is derived from non-sustainable energy crops with high land use. Although global renewable electricity production (60 EJ in 2023) is theoretically sufficient to cover the MeOH demand, strong competition for these resources is expected.

Legislative framework

MeOH produced via the ēQATOR concept can be classified partly as an advanced biofuel and partly as a RFNBO. Break-even calculations indicate that the GHG emission savings compared to fossil fuels required to meet the sustainability criteria can already be achieved in several European countries.

KPIs related to the environment

All project KPIs can be achieved by specific ēQATOR scenarios. All ēQATOR pathways result in zero local emissions from heating. Moreover, when powered by offshore wind in 2050, almost all pathways achieve more than 91 % reduction in the CO₂ footprint compared to the fossil reference. However, when operated with the projected European electricity mix for 2030, only a small subset of ēQATOR scenarios reaches more than a 60 % reduction in GHG emissions.

5.2 Conclusions

Long-term perspective for sustainable MeOH production

- All investigated pathways to renewable MeOH are expected to show overall environmental advantages in the future, as compared to fossil MeOH production, even if the carbon footprint of the latter is reduced through CCS of the emissions arising from the SMR process.
- Considering the limited availability of renewable electricity and biophysically limited sustainable carbon resources, hybrid MeOH pathways – combining biogenic carbon from biogas with renewable electricity – represent the most sustainable technological options. These hybrid pathways may nearly double the carbon use efficiency compared to purely bio-based routes as they fully utilize all the carbon in biogas (both CH₄ and CO₂). Moreover, they show significantly higher electricity use efficiency than fully synthetic MeOH as they take advantage of the chemical energy stored in the biogenic sources.
- Thus, where renewable electricity and biomass residues and biogenic wastes are available, hybrid routes should be used to valorise sustainable carbon sources such as OF-MSW and manure. As the two investigated hybrid concepts, ēQATOR and biomethanation, are comparable in terms of environmental performance, the choice between them depends on other boundary conditions, in particular access to the natural gas grid.
- Where renewable electricity is limited but a connection to the natural gas grid is available, biogas should be upgraded to biomethane and injected to replace fossil CH₄/natural gas in MeOH synthesis plants. Because sustainable carbon sources are biophysically limited and MeOH production competes with other technologies (e.g., aviation fuels and other chemical feedstocks), fully synthetic pathways and measures to minimise the overall MeOH demand will additionally be required. Consequently, in the future, a combination of all available renewable pathways to MeOH will be needed.
- For bio-based or hybrid routes, the environmental impacts also depend on whether the biogas would have otherwise been used to generate electricity and the role this electricity would play in grid stabilisation. In addition to the environmental impacts per t MeOH, resource availability must be considered.
- Increasing demand for biogas, and credits for the digestion of manure (resulting in lower emissions) should not trigger an expansion of livestock numbers, since this would substantially raise other environmental impacts now associated with meat and dairy production. Likewise, concentrating livestock in one area should be avoided to prevent local environmental impacts such as nutrient overload. Regardless of the potential use of OF-MSW for MeOH production, waste generation should also be minimised.
- The environmental impacts of all electricity-dependent pathways – both hybrid and fully synthetic – strongly depend on the carbon intensity of the electricity supply. This includes continuous long-term operation and measures for grid stability. Carbon intensity varies by location and is expected to improve over time. Low-carbon electricity is essential for outperforming fossil MeOH from an environmental point of view.
- Moreover, the specific environmental side effects of certain renewable energy sources should be

considered and mitigated when expanding renewable electricity generation. For example, H₂S emissions from deep geothermal power plants could significantly contribute to acidification if not captured e.g. for sulphuric acid production. Land use implications of electricity from dedicated biomass crops or wood chips should also be considered.

- When environmental impacts of the electricity and materials production are minimised in the future, CH₄ emissions may dominate the system for biogas-based pathways. Thus, a consistent prevention of CH₄ emissions from plant operation and substrate and digestate storage is essential.

Specific insights for ēQATOR

For ēQATOR, the differences in operating conditions — such as MWH vs. RH, DR vs. MR or manure vs. OF-MSW as feedstock — or further process optimisations have only minor effects compared to the influence of the electricity emission factor.

Nevertheless, improvements are still worthwhile where economically feasible. The lowest environmental impacts are achieved when the process uses the most efficient heating technology, applies MR to biogas from OF-MSW, uses H₂ from high-temperature electrolysis and implements advanced heat integration.

Importance of Life Cycle Assessment

LCA is an extremely valuable tool for guiding the development of sustainable carbon value chains. LCA prevents shifting burdens from one life cycle stage to another. LCA enables:

- quantification of environmental impacts,
- identification of hot spots and optimisation potentials, and
- assessment of new and emerging technologies through prospective LCA or ex-ante LCA.

Additionally, potential analyses of renewable resource availability are necessary to provide sound recommendations.

5.3 Recommendations

To the scientific community and industry (process developers)

A shift from fossil MeOH to renewable MeOH based on renewable electricity and sustainable biomass is essential to achieve net-zero targets. Given their marginal differences, all renewable MeOH pathways should not compete but rather complement each other, jointly scaled up to TRL 9 for broad implementation. In the short term, biogas upgrading and subsequent reforming to MeOH in a centralised plant might be the most cost-efficient and environmentally friendly solution. However, in the long term (2050), hybrid pathways and synthetic MeOH using renewable electricity will make most sense due to scarce sustainable carbon availability. The ēQATOR concept offers good use of available resources and is an opportunity for biogas use at locations without access to a CH₄ gas grid.

Given the limited availability of renewable electricity and sustainable carbon sources, we recommend the following procedures according to the sustainability hierarchy of ‘sufficiency’ (reducing demand), ‘consistency’ (using renewable resources), and ‘efficiency’ (optimising processes):

Sufficiency and Consistency: Analysis of the areas where MeOH use can be reduced to lower its demand in 2050.

- One of the most important uses of MeOH is formaldehyde production. Formaldehyde is used in the production of urea-formaldehyde resins for particle boards and fibreboards (among others). Beyond the ongoing phase-out of formaldehyde in these products due to health-related concerns, the adoption of design strategies that emphasize timeless aesthetics, repairability, and the use of

sustainably sourced solid materials — which allow for easy disassembly and reuse — is strongly recommended to enhance the longevity and circularity of furniture products.

- Another main use of MeOH is in biodiesel and gasoline blending. Even though renewable MeOH has a lower environmental impact than fossil MeOH, other energy carriers with lower energy and carbon requirements may be preferable. For example, battery-electric vehicles offer substantially higher energy efficiency than electricity-derived or bio-based fuels.
- Future growth in MeOH demand will primarily come from its use as a feedstock in the methanol-to-olefins (MTO) process for plastics and fibres, which is currently based on petroleum. While this enables sector defossilisation, the expected doubling of plastics production by 2050 versus limited sustainable raw materials makes reducing, reusing, repairing and recycling plastics and textiles essential.

Efficiency

- Promote the expansion of renewable energies. Establish ēQATOR and other processes primarily in countries with a green electricity mix or invest in on-site renewable electricity generation. Do not only consider GHG emissions of renewable energies but also other environmental impacts. Particular attention should be paid to H₂S emissions from deep geothermal plants and to land use impacts of biomass production.
- Optimise renewable MeOH pathways by the expansion and optimisation of direct electric heating (efficiency of electricity-to-heat conversion), heat integration (e.g. the implementation of a heat network including all possible heat sources and sinks such as the compression energy and the electrolyser), the further development of electrolysis technology and the overall carbon yield (e.g. increasing the biogas CH₄ content, integrating side streams, improving downstream treatment).

Beyond those key measures, additional focus can be placed on the following.

- Reduce CH₄ emissions as far as possible. Since CH₄ is a short-lived but potent GHG, its impact is underestimated when using the GWP₁₀₀ metric for near-term targets.
- Use the developed electrification technologies and heat integration strategies also for other processes and invest in research to scale these technologies to the industrial level.
- Grid stabilisation and flexibilization options play a key role in the future renewable energy supply. Invest in research to determine the extent the developed technology can contribute to solving existing energy storage and grid flexibility challenges.
- Integrate LCA indicators into process development, for instance by coupling them with process simulations and economic parameters to directly identify optimization potentials.

To political decision makers and research funding agencies

- Ensure that mandatory regulations are put in place to guarantee that the production of MeOH and other platform chemicals complies with the projected climate path for CO₂ reduction. The entire life cycle must be taken into account, with particular consideration given to end-of-life processes.
- Green electricity is absolutely necessary to ensure low environmental impacts of electrified systems. Fund and guide the expansion of renewable energy, short- and long-term storage and flexible options available to major electricity consumers. Invest in both solar and wind energy to minimise the need for long-term energy storage. Create planning security to enable investments.
- Both MeOH from DAC and electrolysis and MeOH produced from biogas have large advantages compared to conventional, fossil MeOH. Due to resource scarcity, both concepts should be promoted and not be played off against each other. However, the projected MeOH demand cannot easily be met with these technologies. Thus, sufficiency and circularity play an important

role and should be encouraged by appropriate legal framework.

To LCA performers

- Although the IPCC does not assign a default GWP to H₂, its climate impact remains debated. This should be addressed in studies where H₂ is a major component or focus.
- Options promoting flexibility and grid stabilisation should be included when assessing the environmental impact of electricity, particularly if electricity dominates the system.
- Include a resource availability analysis since the most environmentally friendly option per kg may result in a lock-in situation and investment in this option may prevent a globally optimised solution.

Nomenclature and abbreviations

AEM	Anion exchange membrane
AP	Acidification potential
CCS	Carbon capture and storage
CHP	Combined heat and power
COP	Coefficient of Performance
DA	Delegated Act
DAC	Direct air capture
DR	Dry reforming
GHG	Greenhouse gas(es)
GWP	Global warming potential
HTE	High-temperature electrolysis
HT-WGS	High-temperature water-gas shift
IE	Inhabitant equivalents
ILCD	International Reference Life Cycle Data System
ILCSA	Integrated life cycle sustainability assessment
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	(Environmental) life cycle assessment
LC-EIA	Life cycle environmental impact assessment
LCI	Life cycle inventory
LCIA	Life cycle impact assessment
LCT	Life cycle thinking
LHV	Lower heating value
LT-WGS	Low-temperature water-gas shift
LU	Land use
MEA	Monoethanolamine
MWH	Microwave heating
MR	Mixed reforming
NREU	Non-renewable energy use
ODP	Ozone depletion potential
OF-MSW	Organic fraction of municipal solid waste
ORC	Organic Rankine cycle
PEM	Proton exchange membrane
PFD	Process Flow Diagram
PMF	Particulate matter formation
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
RFNBO	Renewable fuel of non-biological origin
RH	Resistive heating
SMR	Steam methane reforming
SOEC	Solid Oxide Electrolyser Cell
t	(Metric) tonne
TEP	Terrestrial eutrophication potential
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

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Appendix

Detailed PFD for scenario A

Figure A1. Detailed PFD of the eQATOR process providing MeOH from manure-based biogas, as well as from renewable electricity and renewable hydrogen. In scenario A, an alternative use of the biogas is considered: on-site power generation in a combined heat and power (CHP) plant.

Detailed PFDs for scenario B

Figure A2. Detailed PFD of the eQATOR process providing MeOH from manure-based biogas, as well as from renewable electricity and renewable hydrogen. In scenario B, an alternative use of the biomass is considered: spreading manure on fields to replace fossil fertiliser.

Figure A3. Detailed PFD of the eQATOR process providing MeOH from OF-MSW-based biogas, as well as from renewable electricity and renewable hydrogen. In scenario B, an alternative use of the biomass is considered: composting the OF-MSW to replace other organic substrates.

Settings for eQATOR process

Table A1. Representative biogas compositions chosen for eQATOR project.

Component	Unit	Manure	OF-MSW
CH ₄	%	55	60
CO ₂	%	39	34
N ₂	%	5	5
O ₂	%	1	1
H ₂ O		Saturation conditions	
H ₂ S	ppm _{dry}	500	500
NH ₃	ppm _{dry}	50	50
Chlorine ^a	ppm _{dry}	0	0
Siloxanes	ppm _{dry}	0	9
Aromatic hydrocarbons	mg/Nm ³ dry	0	0

^a Chlorine is usually negligible in biogas, but will be reduced to ppb levels.

Additional results

Influence of heating technology

In addition to the global warming potential, the influence of heating technology on land use was investigated for the years 2030 and 2050 in Figure A4. As can be seen from Figure A4, the choice of heating technology has only a minor influence on land use attributed to the production of MeOH by the eQATOR concepts.

Figure A4. Life cycle land use from eQATOR methanol (MeOH) for different eQATOR scenarios comparing RH and MWH for 2030 (left) and 2050 (right). **How to read the figure:** See Figure 11.